

INTEGRATING TECHNICAL VOCABULARY INTO ESP CURRICULUM
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Abstract: English is considered main part of the communication in all fields, especially aviation and business. By the help of this, the number of people increased their interest to study in English for Specific Purpose (ESP), and cause to rise demands for this. The present study explores how important vocabulary instruction in ESP curriculum and what kind of differences are there between learning in specific purpose and field-related necessity. The study also highlights recent research on innovative vocabulary learning methods like technology based and digital flashcards. Integrated vocabulary helps improving ESP learner's communicative competence and better preparation for real-life environments.

Key words: *English for Specific Purpose, EFL learners, vocabulary learning, technical vocabulary, self-regulated learning, digital flashcards, communicative competence*

Annotatsiya: Ingliz tili barcha sohalarda, ayniqsa aviatsiya va biznesda muloqotning asosiy qismi hisoblanadi. Buning yordamida odamlarning ingliz tilida o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishi Spesifik maqsadlarda (ESP) oshdi va bunga talablar ortdi. Ushbu tadqiqot ESP o'quv dasturida lug'atni o'qitish qanchalik muhimligini va aniq maqsadda o'rganish va sohaga oid zarurat o'rtasida qanday farqlar mavjudligini o'rganadi. Tadqiqot shuningdek, texnologiyaga asoslangan va raqamli kartalar kabi lug'atni o'rganishning innovatsion usullari bo'yicha so'nggi tadqiqotlarni ta'kidlaydi. Integratsiyalashgan lug'at ESP o'quvchisining kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini yaxshilashga va real hayot muhitiga yaxshiroq tayyorlanishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Maxsus maqsadli ingliz tili, EFL o'rganuvchilari, lug'atni o'rganish, texnik lug'at, o'z-o'zini tartibga soluvchi o'rganish, raqamli kartalar, kommunikativ kompetentsiya*

Аннотация: Английский язык является ключевым элементом коммуникации во всех областях, особенно в авиации и бизнесе. В связи с этим возрос интерес к изучению английского языка для специальных целей (ESP), и, соответственно, увеличился спрос на него. В данном исследовании рассматривается важность обучения лексике в программе ESP и различия между обучением для специальных целей и потребностями данной

области. В исследовании также освещаются последние исследования инновационных методов изучения лексики, таких как использование технологий и цифровых карточек. Интегрированная лексика помогает изучающим ESP улучшить свою коммуникативную компетентность и лучше подготовиться к реальной жизни.

Ключевые слова: *английский язык для специальных целей, изучающие английский как иностранный, изучение лексики, техническая лексика, саморегулируемое обучение, цифровые карточки, коммуникативная компетентность*

Introduction

English is considered the main aid of the communication over the world. This is especially true in international airports and airlines. Chinese EFL (English as a foreign language) learners are well motivated and particularly interested in ESP. The boom in ESP teaching, in both college education and continuing ducation, is a natural result of the growing societal demand for English skills, the rapid development of the field of applied linguistics, and advances in educational psychology. As the technology develops day by day, teaching vocabulary for ESP students differ significantly from ESL students because of their another objectives and various content targets. Designing an English language curriculum is of especially importance for ESP instructors. According to Nunan (1993), the teacher can only fulfill his or her responsibility to develop strong curriculum material if given the time, the skills and support to do so. Such support must not be seen as existing in isolation from the curriculum. The key issues in ESP curriculum design are 1) fostering the ability to communicate successfully in occupational settings; 2) balancing content language acquisition and general language acquisition; 3) designing materials that will work in both heterogeneous and homogenous learner groups; and 4) developing materials (Nunan, 1987: p. 75).

Review of literature

In most cases, teacher should pay more attention to the different factors about their students, for example, student's background knowledge, their interest and curiosity, duration of learning period, knowledge of students and the principles of teaching and learning. ESP students usually have demands on their specific terminology of their fields. Technical vocabulary plays an important role of their necessity in workplace communication. Without sufficient vocabulary, the may encounter to understand these specific materials or express their own perspectives and opinions fluently or accurately. In order to utilize technical vocabulary into ESP curriculum design there are some productive methods and

steps. First of all, teachers should identify the requirement of student's needs and what kind of terms they do want to learn by giving some questionnaires and textbooks. Then, teacher should taught the vocabulary deeply with some practice like teaching them in contexts in order to using this vocabulary in real-life communication. Furthermore, Boroughani et al. (2023)[1]. investigated the use of mobile-assisted self-regulated learning (SRL) for academic vocabulary acquisition. Their study involved 49 university students divided into a mobile-assisted group and a control group. The mobile-assisted group utilized the Lexilize app on their mobile devices for vocabulary learning, while the control group received traditional instruction using word lists. The results indicated that the mobile-assisted SRL group achieved significantly better outcomes on post-treatment tests compared to the control group, suggesting the effectiveness of this approach. This also investigated the effects of DFs on Iranian EFL university students' receptive and productive knowledge of academic vocabulary. The study involved 86 participants divided into three groups: a DFs group using the Anki mobile app, a paper flashcards (PFs) group, and a control group studying from word lists. The findings revealed that the DFs group utilizing the Anki app demonstrated significantly greater improvement in both receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge compared to the participants using paper flashcards and word lists.

Methods

To analyze the qualitative data obtained from the phone interviews, the researchers first translated the interviews into English. During translation, the researchers maintained the integrity of the participants' expressions through precise translation. The translated transcripts were then cleaned to include only information relevant to the research concern. This data was then subjected to content analysis using NVivo software. Content analysis was employed to systematically identify and quantify the frequency of specific words, concepts, or themes within the qualitative data (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005)[2]. The content analysis was conducted using an inductive approach, meaning it was not influenced by any predetermined theoretical framework. Instead, codes and categories were derived directly from the participants' responses. Subsequently, the researcher meticulously scrutinized the data to identify the codes and categories relevant to the second research question. This categorization process facilitated the identification of the major patterns or themes in participants' responses. In this study, the results of the content analysis are presented by reporting the frequency and percentage of the recurring concepts. This approach

facilitated the exploration of the emerging themes with potentially significant implications.

Results

During phone interviews, participants were asked to share their opinions on the effectiveness of the content developed by Storyline software for technical vocabulary learning and the reasons behind it. The findings revealed positive learning outcomes associated with Storyline use. The participants primarily mentioned that Storyline-based content successfully enhanced their motivation, engagement with vocabulary during the learning process, and fostered a more stimulating learning environment, thereby increasing their interest in and persistence with technical vocabulary learning. Participants also emphasized the perceived benefits of using Storyline-based content for technical vocabulary learning. Notably, they mentioned that utilizing Storyline-based content increased their capacity to become more self-directed in the process of technical vocabulary learning and potentially enhance the word retention. Participants also emphasized the perceived benefits of using Storyline-based content for technical vocabulary learning. Notably, they mentioned that utilizing Storyline-based content increased their capacity to become more self-directed in the process of technical vocabulary learning and potentially enhance the word retention.

Discussion

From a broader perspective, the overall findings confirm that the cloud-based infrastructure of Articulate Storyline (Rashid & Chaturvedi, 2019)[3] and its capability to deliver interactive learning materials via slides (Daryanes et al., 2023) can significantly augment technical vocabulary acquisition in ESP contexts by fostering intentional vocabulary learning strategies. In this regard, the cumulative findings of this study corroborate the existing body of research that attests to the efficacy of intentional vocabulary learning approaches in the EFL domain (Laufer et al., 2005; Schmitt, 2008; Soyooof et al., 2022; Webb et al., 2020)[3]. To elucidate this, it is posited that the utilization of Storyline-based content optimizes technical vocabulary acquisition by amplifying the three pivotal facilitating factors intrinsic to intentional vocabulary learning. the overall results indicated that the utilization of Storyline-based content for technical vocabulary learning contributes to the effectiveness of TAVL, an innovative pedagogical approach. This approach possesses the potential to facilitate the technical vocabulary learning process by designing more engaging materials, fostering sustained engagement during vocabulary learning, and boosting students' motivation (Hao et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2021).[2]

Conclusion

The present study examined the efficacy of Articulate Storyline software in augmenting technical vocabulary learning among two cohorts of ESP students. One cohort received Storyline-based content for technical vocabulary, while the other group continued with their traditional instructional method, such as using word lists from their coursebooks. The overall findings of the present study demonstrate that Articulate Storyline software, when employed for technical vocabulary learning, exhibits comparable efficacy to technological tools designed for the same purpose in ESP settings. Moreover, participants exposed to Storyline-based content for technical vocabulary learning expressed a favorable disposition toward this technological tool, citing its efficiency, usability, and advantages. Additionally, the findings provide further evidence that technology-enhanced vocabulary learning in ESP settings surpasses traditional approaches to vocabulary acquisition as evidenced by the EG's superior performance on the post-test relative to the CG. The findings also illustrate that the utilization of Storyline-based content for technical vocabulary learning fostered participants' engagement, enjoyment, motivation, and self-directed learning experiences, comparable to its application for pedagogical purposes in other educational contexts. Finally, the findings indicate that the cloud-based nature of Articulate Storyline and its capacity to deliver interactive learning materials through slides enhance technical vocabulary learning in ESP settings by facilitating intentional vocabulary learning approaches, which have been demonstrated to be influential for vocabulary acquisition in EFL contexts.

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